

Crisis Of Infrastructure and Agricultural Development in Africa: The Case of Nigeria

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Abstract

The importance of agriculture to human survival cannot be overemphasized and this is because it provides food for the world over. For any society to develop and thrive in its agricultural sector there must be on ground requisite infrastructures to aid the development of the sector. This study therefore looks at the prime importance of agriculture and the roles infrastructural facilities play in the development of the sector. Relying mainly on extant literature, quality road networks, post-harvest storage facilities, electricity and telecommunication, amongst many others, have been clearly shown to play critical roles in agricultural development. Inadequacy or lack of these basic infrastructures is capable of impeding agricultural development. The study adopted Adelman's general equilibrium theory of agricultural demand led industrialization (ADLI) which is the view that the linkages between production and consumption in a country's development strategy should be agriculture-driven rather than export-driven and increased agricultural productivity would be the initiator of industrialization. The paper therefore recommends that there should be a broad economic plan in using agriculture to transform the economy of states in Africa, Africa and Nigeria in particular must replace the importation of agricultural produces and materials with their own produce, which would in turn reduce poverty, enhance food and nutrition security, and provide sustainable growth to the respective societies.

Keywords: Africa, Agriculture, Crisis of infrastructure, Infrastructural development, Nigeria

Introduction

The centrality of agriculture to human continued existence cannot be overemphasized. Food is perhaps the most important of the basic needs of life, besides the need for shelter, clothing and security; as without food the facility to sponsor or strive for other needs takes the back seat, compelling the generality of man's activities to center on meeting this prime need. Beyond meeting the food need of the population, agricultural production also provides employment, income and foreign exchange, and the needed resources for the growth of other non-agricultural sectors. Creating a sustainable agricultural development path therefore means creating growth potentials for the country by ensuring enough food for present and future generations and generating sufficient income for development.

In line with this, many states and governments have listed it as an imperative that strong emphasis be placed on the expansion of the capacity of agriculture with a view to ensuring food sufficiency and realizing economic potentials through agriculture. This position is hinged on the certainty that agriculture has been key in the overall development of many countries such as the United States, China, Indonesia, Thailand and Japan. As noted by Clute (2014) agriculture, beyond ensuring food sufficiency has played a key role in the capitalization of the industrialization process of these countries. For Macatta (2016) if the process of economic development is to be initiated and made self-sustaining, it must begin with the agricultural sector. The aim of this paper is to critically analyze the infrastructural challenges of agricultural development in Africa and its implications for sustainable development.

Agriculture and Sustainable development

An adequate food base has been identified as an essential prerequisite for development, Clute (2014) argues that agricultural development is a necessary precondition for social, political and economic development of nations. Even in cases where the country is fortunate enough to have other resources which can be exported to finance food imports, Clute (2014) noted that such imports would detract from the accumulation of capital necessary for industrialization and would be unwise from a developmental standpoint. This ideology has driven the emphasis of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) of 2015 on the development of agriculture as a way of increasing development potentials and meeting the material needs of the populace.

Agricultural development explains the processes that create the conditions for the fulfillment of *agricultural* potentials, particularly in terms of providing assistance to crop producers with the help of various agricultural resources, providing protection for agricultural activities, assisting in the research sphere, employing latest techniques, controlling pests and facilitating diversity. Agricultural development also involves ensuring and maintaining productive capacity for the

present and the future while increasing productivity without damaging the environment or jeopardizing natural resources.

Investing in agricultural development addresses not only the problem of food security but also other socio-economic challenges including poverty; lack of water and energy use; climate change; and unsustainable production and consumption. Schultz (1953); Kuznets (1966); Dethier and Effenberger (2011) have noted how agriculture has been a source that induces industrial growth and a structural transformation of economies. For Schultz (1953) agriculture is important for economic growth in the sense that it guarantees subsistence for society without which growth is not possible in the first place. This view on the role of agriculture in economics also matched the empirical observation made by Kuznets (1966) that the importance of the agricultural sector declines with economic development. In this view, agriculture's role in economic development is to supply cheap food and low wage labour to the modern sector. Otherwise, both sectors have few interconnections. As noted by Dethier and Effenberger, (2011), growth and higher productivity in the agricultural sector contributes to overall economic growth by releasing labour as well as capital to other sectors in the economy. Macatta (2016) have also noted that agriculture contributes to development and sustainability of nations in the following ways: by providing food and raw material to non- agricultural sectors of the economy, by creating demand for goods produced in non-agricultural sectors, by increasing the purchasing power of the rural people through their access to marketable surplus, by providing investable surplus in the form of savings and taxes to be invested in non-agricultural sector, by earning valuable foreign exchange through the export of agricultural products and by providing employment to a vast army of uneducated, backward and unskilled labour. A case in point is the successes of agricultural development in India. As noted by Madhusudhan (2015) **agriculture** is the most important sector of the **Indian Economy**. Indian agriculture sector accounts for 18% of India's gross domestic product (GDP) and provides **employment** to 50% of the countries **workforce**. Currently, India is the world's largest producer of rice, wheat, spices and spice products, amongst many other produces such as dairy, meat, poultry, fisheries and food grains etc. India has emerged as the second **largest producer** of fruits and vegetables in the world. According to data provided by the Department of Economics and Statics (DES), the production of food grains for the year 2013-2014 is 264 million tons which is increased when compared to 257million tons in 2012-2013. Today, India ranks second worldwide in farm output. In 2013, India exported \$38 billion worth of agricultural products, making it the seventh largest agricultural exporter worldwide and the sixth largest net exporter. Most of its agriculture exports serve developing and least developed nations. Indian agricultural/horticultural and processed foods are exported to more than 120 countries, primarily in the Middle East, Southeast Asia, SAARC countries, the EU and the United

States (Madhusudhan, 2015). This kind of growth increases the capacity for sustainability as it creates immediate and future potentials for development.

In Africa, agriculture is projected to play a key role not only in the provision of the food needed to feed the rapidly growing population. but also the resources needed for industrialization and for bringing the continent into the industrial and technical age. Scholars such as Schiff and Valdez (1992), Fan, Zhang and Rao (2004). Timmer (2005), have argued that the agricultural sector has sufficient scale and growth-linkages to significantly influence aggregate growth and development in Africa. While the provision of sufficient food for the growing population puts agriculture at the center of current growth and development issues in Africa, agriculture also supplies raw materials to the industrial sector which is critical for industrial growth and development.

Although the advantage of the connection between agriculture and non-agriculture in achieving the growth and development process had long been recognized, Africa is yet to experience exponential growth. For a continent with a vast arable area for farming, a thriving young population and a favourable tropical climate, it is surprising that Africa is not a net exporter of agricultural products. Veras (2017) noted that in the 1970s, Africa provided 8% of the world's total agricultural exports, however today this number has dropped to a negligible 2%. Furthermore, Africa spends roughly US \$40bn per annum through inordinate food imports; a statistic which is expected to almost triple to an estimated \$110bn by 2025 in the face of the rapid population growth and food needs of the continent (Veras, 2017; Kalibata, 2017). The implications of these manifests in the various underdevelopment challenges befuddling the continent such as the growing poverty and unemployment statistics, the recalcitrant spate of conflict between livelihood groups in various States in Africa, etc.

A number of issues have been adduced for the poor performance of agriculture in Africa. Veras (2017) and Kalibata (2017), amongst many other scholars, have identified technical issues, resource constraints, poor policies, conflict, and many other socio-economic problems and organizational constrains as major impediments of the business of agriculture in Africa.

The role of infrastructure in agricultural development in Africa

Agriculture, which was largely the mainstay of many Africa economies prior to the discovery of certain extractive resources, has suffered serious neglect. The development impact of agricultural growth in African is enormous, as it has a direct effect on food security, organizational productivity, employment, peace and even poverty reduction, given that 50% of the African population is directly engaged in Agriculture. As noted by Gango and Lukoma (2011) agricultural

growth is substantial for Africa, without agricultural productivity growth, a critical step in the process of economic transformation and growth in many states in Africa would be missed. Also, in recognition of the critical role that agriculture holds for the continent's development. African Heads of State and Government in 2003 adopted the Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Program (CAADP), to combat poverty and hungry CAADP is the African Union's (AU) official agenda for spurring agricultural development in Africa. Its principles stress the inclusiveness of processes with meaningful involvement of farmers' organizations, civil society and the private sector-as well as the integration of agriculture and food security in overall development policies. In spite of these efforts at improving agriculture in Africa, many challenges still abound. Africa still produces below expected par, and largely for subsistence. Modern day agriculture is not subsistence focused; it is a basis for commerce and industry. It thus becomes imperative that the enabling facilities and conditions that will drive the goal of agricultural development be fashioned or at least improved upon. Most prominent of these required conditions is largely in the realm of infrastructural development. As noted by Chandrachud and Gajalakshmi (2005) infrastructure development of any economy includes development of both economic infrastructure and social infrastructure. The economic infrastructure can be achieved through developing various sectors like Energy, Power. Telecommunication. Transport (including railways, roadways, airways and seaways), Irrigation. Information Technology and finance etc. On the other hand, the social infrastructure development can be achieved through Education infrastructure development and Health infrastructure development. As noted by Calestous Juma, a Professor of the Practice of International Development at the Harvard Kennedy School and co-chair of the African Union's High-Level Panel on Science, Technology and Innovation, the agriculture sector is highly dependent on energy, telecommunications, water security and transportation and so there is a close alignment between improving infrastructure and global development. If farmers in the continent are to produce enough food to feed a growing population, whilst also sustaining a living from agriculture, sufficient infrastructure needs to be in place. Infrastructure can connect farmers with global markets, linking them to the inputs needed for the sector to survive (Nsehe, 2012). Africa continues to suffer from low levels of agricultural productivity and suffer inability to feed itself and stimulate rural entrepreneurship largely owing to poor infrastructure. According to the World Bank report of 2008, the continent's infrastructure deficit is considered one of the most significant barriers to sustaining Africa's growth. It is estimated that the continent will need to invest nearly \$93 billion per year over the next decade to bridge the deficit. Some estimates put the budget for Nigeria alone at \$15 billion per year. South Africa's plan is part of a long-term infrastructure strategy to be implemented over the next 15 years at the cost of \$462 billion (Nsehe, 2012).

Scholars such as Jegede (1992), Adeniyi (2012) and Tunde & Adeniyi (2012), have identified the importance of infrastructure development, especially in areas of transportation, irrigation and storage facilities, etc., to the growth of agriculture. According to Tunde and Adeniyi (2012) transport is regarded as an important factor involved in agricultural development all over the world. It is the only means by which food produced at farm site is moved to different homes as well as markets. Transport creates market for agricultural produce, enhances interaction among geographical and economic regions and opens up new areas to economic focus. Aderamo and Magaji (2010) cited in Tunde and Adeniyi (2012), also noted that transportation constitutes the main avenue through which different parts of the society are linked together. There is no denying the fact that transport is the most common, pervasive and complex network of the transformation. It covers a wide range, physically convenient, highly flexible and usually the most operationally suitable and readily available means of movement of goods and passenger traffic over short, medium and long distances (Jegede, 1992). Transportation is a big issue for most farmers in Africa. It is either there is lack of access roads from rural areas to urban centers or there are unaffordable transportation charges for the available routes (Tunde and Adeniyi, 2012). The cost of rural transport in Africa is prohibitively high. The cost of road freight in Africa is three times that of other developing regions. Burkina Faso has the lowest cost of rural transport in Africa and is only topped by Gabon, which comes in at US\$ 30.98. High transport costs reduce profits on agricultural products thereby discouraging production (Africa Monitor, 2012). Roads are very important infrastructures that can aid the development of agriculture in Africa. Also, post-harvest storage facilities and/or warehousing have been identified as critical to the growth of agricultural activities. Storage ensures that farm produce do not perish before they get to the end users because of inadequacy or lack of facilities where they can be stored.

Irrigation, listed as one of CAADP's strategies for agricultural development, also plays a key role in the sustainable agriculture. Improving agriculture can only be attained with sustainable land management and reliable water control systems. Irrigation has the potential to contribute immensely towards rural communities' ability to generate income. Its direct impacts can include higher incomes through higher yields, cropping intensity and diversification towards higher value crops; higher rural employment.

Theoretical Framework

This paper explains the importance of the matrix of relationship between agriculture, sustainable development and infrastructural facilities using the Adelman's general equilibrium theory of agricultural demand led industrialization (ADLI). For Adelman (1984) cited in Dethier and Effenberger (2011), owing to the linkages between production and consumption, a country's development strategy should be agriculture-driven rather than export-driven and increased agricultural productivity would be the initiator of industrialization. Moreover, emphasis should be placed on small-to-medium-size farmers because they are more likely to use domestically produced intermediate goods as opposed to large-scale producers who might import machinery and other inputs, which would weaken the linkages between agriculture and other sectors.

The main goal of ADLI is to attain fast and broad-based development within the agricultural sector and to make this sector's development to power broad economic growth. For Dey (2003), ADLI recognizes that cost-reducing technological change increased agricultural productivity and therefore increased rural incomes. Increased rural incomes provided a demand boost for manufactured goods both for consumption as well as for use in agricultural production. The increased demand for domestically manufactured goods raised wages which in turn were spent on the consumption of agricultural output. On the labor side of the market, as agricultural productivity increased, labor shifted from the agricultural sector to the manufacturing sector. Thus, the industrialization of the population was achieved at pace with the labor transition and was based on increased agricultural productivity attained through the use of appropriate technology.

Dethier and Effenberger (2011) noted that the fact that there are important linkages between the traditional and modern sectors in developing countries makes agricultural growth an important instrument for decreasing poverty. For instance, the contribution to poverty reduction takes place directly, through the effects of agricultural growth on farm employment and profitability, and indirectly because increases in agricultural output induce job creation in upstream and downstream non farmer food response to higher domestic demand. Potentially lower food prices increase the purchasing power of poor consumers.

Agricultural programs and Implementation in Africa; the Nigerian case

Agriculture in the context of the economy is tied to various sectors and is essential for generating broad based growth necessary for development. Suffice it to say that Agriculture is fundamental to the sustenance of life and is the bedrock of economic development, especially in the provision of adequate and nutritious food so vital for human development and industrial raw materials for

industry. For any country to have sustainable agricultural development there must be good and efficient infrastructures to corroborate this.

There have been various efforts by government all over Africa to establish Programmes for Agricultural development. In this section a few Agricultural programmes that have been established in Nigeria for the aid of development in the sector, particularly the DFFRI, are discussed.

1. The National Accelerated Food Production Project (NAFPP): The project was launched in 1973, it was an impact-making agricultural strategy to increase food production in specific areas and subsectors of the agricultural economy. The scheme was a well-considered programme for rural development, especially in the area of food production.

2. Operation Feed the Nation (OFN): The programme was launched in 1976, the then Head of State, Gen. Olusegun Obasanjo. The objectives of OFN are as follows:

- a. To mobilize the nation towards self-sufficiency and self-reliance in food production
- b. To encourage the sector of the community relying heavily on food purchase to grow their own food
- c. To encourage pride in Agriculture
- d. To encourage balance nutritional feeding and thereby produced a healthy nation. The operation feed the nation was not specially a rural development strategy, but the rural areas benefited through inputs and professional advice. However, Olusegun and Olufokunbi (1986) observed that the operation feed the nation rather than solve food problems create opportunities for the ruling class to appropriate national funds.

3. Green Revolution: it is a crash programme launched in 1980 by Alhaji ShehuShagari's Administration. Its aim was to boost food production in a bid to provide food to every Nigerian. The objectives of Green Revolution include:

- a. Make the country self-sufficient in food production within 5 years.
- b. To return the country to its pre-eminent crop production stage within 7 years.

4. Directorate for Food, Road and Rural Infrastructure: It was established in 1986 by Gen. Ibrahim Babangida to enhance rural development. This was meant to provide feeder roads, electricity, potable water and toilet facilities for rural dwellers. The establishment of DFFRI was not only a radical department from the previous programmes, but also recognized the complementariness associated with basic needs such as food, shelter, potable water etc. DFFRI can be perceived as an integrated rural development strategy, which includes provision of Economic and social infrastructures. production of Agricultural inputs, Development and Dissemination of Improved Technology to enhance agricultural and rural housing and mobilization for mass participation in rural development. Provision of Economic and Social

Infrastructure: DFFRI developed rural access roads. Government Survey indicated that 60,000km of rural feeder roads were either constructed or rehabilitated under the first phase which was completed in 1987. From the time of inception in 1986 and 1992, DFFRI had completed of over 278,526km of roads, over 5,000 rural communities benefited from its rural electrocution Programme. Also, on water supply to rural communities, 4,000 boreholes/wells were reported to have been sunk by 1980. Another 1, 291, 11,310 and 18,680 wells and boreholes were sunk in 1990, 1991 and 1992 respectively (Ekpoand Olaniyi, 1995).

In spite of all these lofty policies and efforts to resuscitate agriculture in Nigeria, very few have been achieved in the sector. The under-productivity of this sector can be traced to the issues relating to access and use of land, poor government support, ineffective tax reliefs on agricultural activities, policy paralysis in terms of agricultural development, the Dutch disease ushered in by the discovery and concentration on oil as the only resource for the country, poor investment plans by state and private bodies in agriculture, conflict and communal clashes and above all the challenge of infrastructural crisis holding many sectors to ransom in the country. According to Victor Olowe, the Programme Coordinator, Farmers Development Union (FADU), the investment in rural roads would link farmers and their produce to profitable markets (Essiet, 2014). For Olowe, sufficient and quality roads between farms and markets would enable farmers transform their business, as roads would link them to vital input, such as seeds and fertilizer, while also offering them access to competitive markets where they have the opportunity to sell produce for a better price (Essiet, 2014). The Nigerian government cannot talk about encouraging farmers to make farming a business without investing in infrastructure to enable them move their produce from their farms to available markets. For agriculture to thrive as a business, he said government needs to ensure that roads, railways and airports are boosting and not hindering the link between the farms and the markets. By ensuring that produce arrive on time to link with consumers in local towns and cities, he said farmers have the opportunity to compete with one another (Essiet, 2014).

Agriculture in Nigeria continues to suffer from weak linkages with other sectors, including agro-processing and agribusiness, fragmented markets and weak regional integration of commodity chains, and at the same time is vulnerable to external shocks due to poor infrastructure, poor financing and investment from state and private bodies, inelastic commodity demand and the challenge of price volatility. The far-reaching implication is that Nigeria will not be able to locally meet the food and material needs for exponential industrialization and growth without depending on external economies.

Implications of Poor infrastructure on Agricultural development

As noted by Oke (2017) the key to unlocking Africa's economic potential lies with addressing the severe infrastructure deficit. Specifically with regard to agriculture, the state of roads and storage facilities in Africa pose a significant hurdle for farmers. The poor state of the continent's roads and storage facilities results in a substantial loss of large proportions of agricultural production. According to a World Bank report in 2011, the amount of grains losses in sub-Saharan Africa annually amounts to US \$4bn each. which in turn is more than the amount of annual food aid received in the region and equivalent to the annual caloric requirement of 48 million people (Oke, 2017). Also, the African Postharvest Losses Information system (APHLIS) estimates that between 10% and 23% of total cereal production waste in Africa post-harvest. Of this between 2%-5% are lost owing to poor storage systems, about 2% occurs during the transport to the market phase and another 2% 4% goes to waste in the market storage facilities (Oke, 2017). In fact, a study undertaken in Uganda, Tanzania, and Kenya in 2008, found that transport costs make up about 76% of total maize marketing costs, while the remainder of the losses typically occurs on the farm level (Oke, 2017). According to Professor Juma, poor road network, amongst other deficiencies, is a major concern for agricultural development. African farmers without adequate road networks are condemned to grow not what they can eat, but what they can carry on their heads and eat quickly before pests destroy it. As a result, nearly half of the hungry people in Africa are farmers. The majority of Africa's rural populations do not live within reach of all-season roads. As a result, they are not capable of participating in any meaningful entrepreneurial activities. On average, in middle- income countries about 60% of rural people live within two kilometers of an all-season road. In Kenya, for example, only about 32% of the rural people live within two kilometers of an all-weather road. The figure is 31% for Angola, 26% for Malawi, 24% for Tanzania, 18% for Mali and a mere 10.5% for Ethiopia. Expanding rural road networks (in addition to investing in electrification and irrigation) is a strategic investment for rural development and should not be judged against narrowly defined economic criteria (Nsehe, 2012).

The implications are enormous, especially with a growing world population and the burden of growth on the environment. Poor infrastructure, and by extension poor agriculture, impacts on extremely on food security. With the global population estimated in reach 9 billion by year 2050, farmers will have to produce 70% more food. Meanwhile, the world is yet to meet the food needs of the current teeming population. Underdeveloped agriculture also affects economic growth and industrialization, as the needed materials for manufacturing and technological advancement are under-produced or in most cases sourced from outside the continent and therefore creating capital flight. Environmental scarcity has also been identified as a major source of conflict in developing countries. Ahmadvand and Karami (2007) noted that scarcity of natural resources such as land,

water, forest etc, which can arise from depletion or degradation, increased demand or unequal distribution has immense impact of conflict between livelihood groups.

Conclusion

In all ramifications, agricultural development has been proven crucial for sustainable development. The positive expansion of agriculture has a direct effect on all ramifications of the society. Agriculture is the lifeline of Africa. It holds the key to eliminating hunger, providing employment, reducing conflict, ensuring food security and driving industrialization. As noted earlier, the implications of an underdeveloped agriculture are enormous, especially with a growing world population and the burden of growth on food security and how agriculture is extremely detrimental to food security and has been identified as a source of conflict, poverty and unemployment. The thesis of this paper is that through infrastructural development, industrialization that expansion of the economy can be achieved. This has been proven in countries like Thailand, China, Japan, the United States, etc where massive investments are made into improving agriculture to meet the food needs and material needs of the society. The reverse has been the case in states in Africa. With very few countries in the continent such as Ethiopia, South Africa and Zimbabwe investing in Agriculture, many, including Nigeria still contend with food scarcity and other attendant problems of an underdeveloped agriculture.

Recommendations

An increase in productivity, matched with the right set of policies and investment could revert the poor situation of agriculture in Africa. Raising productivity in agriculture is vital to transformative growth, not just because it has the potential to expand markets by displacing imports, but also because agricultural growth is twice as effective in reducing poverty as growth in non-agricultural sectors. This change begins with a broad economic plan to use agriculture to transform the economy of states in Africa. Africa must replace the importation of agricultural produces and materials with their own produce, which would in turn reduce poverty, enhance food and nutrition security, and provide sustainable growth to the respective societies.

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